

Justice at the Doorstep of Citizens through Gram Nyayalayas Act, 2008 : A Critical View

Ashok K. Sharma

Associate Professor & Head
Department of Law
J.V. Jain College, Saharanpur, U.P.

Received : 16/10/2020

1st BPR : 28/10/2020

2nd BPR : 06/11/2020

Accepted : 19/11/2020

Abstract

In the administration of justice the main problem has been that of delayed justice. Even after some efforts Indian judicial system has not been able to deliver justice in a reasonably well-time-bound manner to its people. More particularly the poor people and rural populace are the worst victims to this mal-administration of justice. The Gram Nyayalaya Act, 2008 has been specially designed to answer this problem of delayed justice particularly in terms of diluting criminal procedure as well as civil procedure, and in terms of rigid rules of Evidence Act. But wherever the need be, State Governments in consultation with respective High Courts will act in superintendence so that minimum legal standards may be observed while dispensing with small matters of rural people, whether they are of criminal nature or of civil nature. Decision by consensus has been preferred, and adjournments of the cases have been discouraged.

Keywords: Administration of justice, Criminal procedure, Civil procedure.

Introduction

Right from the independence of the country India has been striving to provide justice particularly to its poor people so that the highly placed objects of the constitution may be achieved like that of many welfare legislative Acts have been passed to better India's Administration of justice keeping in view the genuine interests of many sections of our country's mass population e.g. women, children, labour class, tribal people and particularly our poor class and rural populace.

In this background one more welfarist piece of legislation is before us, and it is the establishment of Gram Nyayalayas Act, 2008, the object of which is very noble one and that is to provide real access to justice to Indian citizens at their very doorsteps. This Act applies to the whole of India except the State of J&K, States of Nagaland, Arunachal Pradesh, Sikkim and the Tribal Areas of the States of Assam, Meghalaya, Tripura and Mizoram listed in the Sixth Schedule of our Constitution.

Gram Nyayalayas : Its Constitution and Working

The provision for establishment of one or more Gram Nyayalayas for every Panchayat at intermediate level has been conceived and planned and the same is to be decided by the State Government in consultation with the High Court of that State by notification. These Panchayats are the basic units of self-Government under the concept of establishing local self-governance as contemplated under Constitution (73rd Amendment) Act, 1992⁽¹⁾ for which Part IX has been inserted in the Constitution. For formation of such Panchayats at intermediate level in a district, the population should be atleast twenty lacs and above. Let us briefly explain what is this intermediate level : it means a level between the village and the district level as per Article 243(c) of our Constitution.

By notification of the State Government, Headquarter of a Gram Nyayalaya will be at the Headquarter of the Intermediate Panchayat. Such Gram Nyayalaya will be presided over by a Nyayadhikari. Nyayadhikari is to be appointed by the State Government in consultation with the High Court. As per Chapter III of this Act the Nyayadhikari must be eligible to be appointed as a Judicial Magistrate of the Ist Class.⁽²⁾ Per section 6(2) of the Act⁽³⁾, provision for giving representation to Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, Women and other classes and

communities is to be specified by the State Government. As regards, salary, allowances and other conditions of service of Gram Nyayadhi, they will be such as applicable to the Judicial Magistrate of the First Class.

Providing Procedure of Justice – Simple and Rigid Free

The ever yawning problem of heavy-loaded arrears in Indian Courts and its allied problems that proved disastrous in the justice-delivery system, Law Commission in its 114th Report⁽⁴⁾ made creative suggestions for Alternative Forum for quickest Resolution of Disputes at Grassroot Level i.e. at Rural level.

Further, to advance the Constitutional philosophy of peoples' participation in the administration of justice, the Commission gave the suggestion of an institution to be headed by a legally trained Judge. The Law Commission further recommended some more quick justice delivery points i.e. assembling of the Court will in the village where dispute arose; settlement of the dispute the same day when hearing the parties and examining the evidence took place. Officers of the Revenue Department will help in the above judicial process. The decision in the case will preferably by by consensus and if necessary, by Majority. The decision will be well-reasoned, and in the local language. Law Commission particularly advised against adjournment and change of venue.

Happily, the Gram Nyayalaya Act, 2008 incorporated the above recommendations, and it came into effect from October 2, 2009.

Provision for Mobile Court

As per Section 9 of the Act, Nyayadhikari has to compulsorily visit the villages under his jurisdiction and conduct the proceedings or trial at a place where the parties ordinarily reside.⁽⁵⁾ These Mobile Court can be moved to the places where a cause of action, whether partly or wholly, arose. Per Section 17 the State Government will provide all necessary ministerial aid and other employee to the Gram Nyayalayas.

Jurisdiction Conferred on Gram Nyayalayas

These Nyayalayas have been given both civil and criminal jurisdiction as per Schedule Ist and Schedule IInd of the Act.

- 1. Criminal Jurisdiction** – Gram Nyayadhikari will take cognizance of an offence on a complaint or on a police report. Part I, II and III of the First Schedule of the Act enumerates such offences. Part I contains such offences under IPC for which the punishment does not exceed two years imprisonment. He will also try cases of theft and receiving or retaining stolen property where the value of the property does not exceed rupees twenty thousand, and also the offences under Sections 454, 456, 504 and 506. Part II lists certain Acts like Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, maintenance order under Chapter XII of Cr.P.C., 1973. And the offences in Part III will be notified by the State Government.

As regards the procedure in criminal trial this Act, the Nyayalaya will not generally follow the procedure of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 except where it expressly provides this procedure. Section 20 provides for plea bargaining in which the provisions of the Chapter XXI A of Cr.P.C., 1973 will apply. The cases of complaint will be conducted by Assistant Public Prosecutor per Section 25 of Cr.P.C.

As to the question of appeals in criminal matters from the decision of Gram Nyayalaya, the answer is that this Act restricts the right to appeal. The provisions of Cr.P.C. dealing with appeal will not apply.

- 2. Jurisdiction of Gram Nyayalaya In Civil Matters** – The Second Schedule of the Act lists all suits and proceedings of civil nature, and Gram Nyayalaya has exclusive jurisdiction to try them. As to the right to purchase property, use of common pasture, regulation and timing of taking water from irrigation channel, they all being civil in nature, the Nyayalaya has got jurisdiction in this respect. A few other matters of the enjoyment of civil nature are right to draw water from a well or a tube well, the possession of farm houses where this Nyayalaya has jurisdiction the Nyayalaya will also have jurisdiction to decide cases under the Payment of Wages Act, 1936, and the claims under the Minimum Wages Act, 1948. The pecuniary limit of these Nyayalayas shall be specified by High Court in Consultation with the State Government.

Generally, the provisions of the Code of Civil Procedure, 1908 will not apply to the Gram Nyayalaya, except where made applicable. The mode of filing civil suit will be through making an application to Gram Nyayalaya with a fee that will not be more than Rs. One Hundred. The judgment of this Nyayalaya will be

deemed to be a decree of the Court under C.P.C. and the same would be executable under C.P.C. The decision of the Nyayalaya is final in the following cases and no appeal or revision would lie : (a) where the judgment or order is passed with the consent of the parties; (b) where the matter of the suit is less than five hundred rupees; or (c) where the suit is less than Rs. 5,000/- value and no question of law is involved.

As per Sec. 34 of this Act, an appeal from the judgment or order of this Nyayalaya will lie to the District Court, except the above three categories of cases. However, High Court under Article 227 of the Constitution has superintendence over all Courts and tribunals within its territorial jurisdiction, and Gram Nyayalayas are included in this power. However, the provisions of C.P.C. are not applicable to these Nyayalayas.

One more noteworthy feature of the Gram Nyayalayas is the availability of Conciliation method of Dispute Settlement. Under Article 26 of this Act provides for such conciliation.⁶⁾ This conciliation is to be done with the help of conciliators. High Court will prescribe qualifications for selecting such persons from among the panel of social workers of the village having integrity. As to the applicability of evidence rules Nyayalayas may take such evidence as will help it in resolving the case, without adhering to the rigidity of evidence rules.

Thus, we see that Gram Nyayalayas have been consciously excluded from observing the rigid procedural technicalities of law in order to make such a judicial institution at rural India for the sake of cheap and quick justice delivery system. Let us hope for its realistic and efficient implementation for the poor populace of the country.

References

1. Constitution (Seventy Third Amendment) Act, 1992
2. The Gram Nyayalaya Act, 2008, Chapter III
3. The Gram Nyayalaya Act, 2008, Sec. 6(2)
4. 114th Report of the Law Commission of India
5. The Gram Nyayalaya Act, 2008, Sec. 9
6. The Gram Nyayalaya Act, 2008, Sec. 26

